

Editorial

From The Desk of Guest Editor.....

Proximal Restorations and Pulpal Health Management

Introduction

With advancements in biomaterials, vital pulp therapy has emerged as a promising approach for clinicians. The prevalence of deep proximal carious lesions is notably high, making proximal restorations crucial for maintaining both pulpal and periodontal health. The primary goal in managing deep carious lesions is to preserve pulp vitality, ensuring the long-term survival of the tooth. However, deep proximal lesions that extend close to a healthy pulp pose significant clinical challenges. These lesions not only reach deep into the pulp but also extend towards the cervical margins, leading to substantial loss of tooth structure. Their subgingival location further complicates isolation, accessibility, and the attainment of an optimal seal, particularly when the cervical margins lack enamel and are surrounded by dentin or cementum¹.

Challenges in Managing Deep Proximal Lesions

The management of deep proximal lesions is complex due to multiple factors. The subgingival nature of these lesions creates difficulties in rubber dam isolation, visibility, and accessibility during cavity preparation. Additionally, placement, finishing, and polishing of the restoration at the cervical margin become technically demanding². The intricate nature of these procedures necessitates the use of advanced tools such as magnification devices, digital radiography, and dental handpieces equipped with LED lights to ensure precise and effective treatment.

Classification of Deep Carious Dentin Lesions

Deep carious dentin lesions are categorized based on their extent of penetration. A deep carious lesion radiographically extends into the pulpal quarter of the dentin but retains a well-defined zone of radiopaque dentin separating the infected, demineralized dentin from the pulp. In contrast, an extremely deep carious lesion extends through the entire thickness of the dentin, often lacking a radiopaque barrier between the lesion and the pulp³. In such cases, microbial invasion reaches the tertiary dentin and the pulp, increasing the risk of pulpal inflammation and infection⁴. Despite the clinical significance, the precise degree of carious lesion penetration is rarely described in literature concerning vital pulp therapy (VPT) due to the heterogeneity of carious lesions⁵.

Pulpal Response to Carious Lesions

The thickness of the remaining dentin plays a critical role in pulpal response. As carious lesions progress, gram-negative bacteria release lipopolysaccharides (LPS), which diffuse through dentinal tubules and interact with Toll-like receptors 4 (TLR-4) on pulp nociceptors. These nociceptors extend within 0.16 mm of the dentinal tubules, producing an early warning signal to the pulp and the patient³. On a molecular level, metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) expression is triggered only when tissue breakdown occurs in the pulp, serving as a marker for pulpal inflammation severity. Interestingly, MMP-9 levels can be measured from blood samples of an exposed pulp, providing a potential diagnostic tool for evaluating pulpal health⁶.

Management Strategies for Deep Proximal Lesions

Deep proximal lesions in cases where the pulp remains healthy but is not exposed can be managed using indirect pulp capping followed by direct restoration. Direct restorations are cost-effective, require reduced chair time, and necessitate fewer clinical sessions, making them a preferred choice for both clinicians and patients. However, given the presence of bacteria and specific dentin microstructures, adequate dentin preparation is essential prior to placing pulp-preserving materials such as calcium silicate cement⁷. The use of sodium hypochlorite and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) over caries-affected dentin before material placement enhances the tooth-material interface and bonding strength.

In cases where pulpal exposure occurs, effective management involves controlling hemorrhage and reducing bacterial load. Sodium hypochlorite is widely used for hemostasis due to its efficacy in controlling bleeding and decontaminating the pulp. This is followed by the application of calcium silicate cement, which promotes reparative dentin formation without tunnel defects, thereby improving long-term prognosis⁷.

Clinical Perspectives on Pulp Exposure Management

From a clinical standpoint, pulp exposure presents both advantages and challenges. Direct exposure of the pulp to the oral cavity allows for the precise placement of biomaterials in direct contact with the pulp, facilitating better evaluation and management of pulpal health, including assessing pulpal bleeding. However, avoiding pulp exposure is often advantageous as it minimizes the risk of bacterial contamination and preserves the

odontoblast layer, which plays a crucial role in reactionary or reparative dentinogenesis. Additionally, dentin serves as a reservoir for growth factors that are released by capping materials and contribute to the reparative process. Given the tubular structure of dentin, if the remaining dentin thickness is less than 1 mm, it becomes permeable to bacterial challenges, mimicking a pulp exposure scenario⁸.

Pulp Capping vs. Pulpotomy

The choice between pulp capping and pulpotomy depends on the extent of pulpal involvement. Pulp capping involves the direct placement of biomaterials over an exposed pulp without tissue removal⁹. In contrast, pulpotomy involves the either removal of 2–3 mm of pulp tissue at the exposure site or in some cases, the complete removal of the coronal pulp to eliminate infected or inflamed tissue, allowing for a healthier pulpal environment for biomaterial placement⁷.

Assessing Pulpal Hemostasis and Inflammation

Effective assessment of pulpal hemostasis is essential in determining the degree of inflammation. Increased vascular permeability and hyperemia associated with inflammation can prolong bleeding, necessitating at least five minutes for hemostasis under normal physiological conditions. If bleeding persists beyond this timeframe, it may indicate residual inflammation, requiring further pulp removal until healthy, non-inflamed tissue is exposed⁷.

Failure Patterns in Deep Proximal Lesion Management

An analysis of existing literature highlights two distinct failure patterns in deep caries management:

1. Early failures, occurring within days of treatment, leading to symptomatic pulpitis. These failures are often linked to the misdiagnosis of pulpitis severity and inadequate pulp tissue removal.
2. Long-term failures, detected several months post-treatment, typically associated with apical lesions resulting from pulp necrosis and subsequent root canal infection. These failures are commonly attributed to compromised sealing ability of the restoration or breakdown of the mineralized bridge, allowing secondary infection³.

Influence of Various Factors on Pulpal Response

Several factors influence pulpal response to restorations, including bacterial contamination, remaining dentin thickness, material biocompatibility, and postoperative time. Studies have shown that pulpal response diminishes over time. In accordance with the Federation Dentaire Internationale (FDI) standards, research recommends evaluating pulpal healing over both short-term and long-term periods. An *in vivo* study demonstrated a significant reduction in thermal sensitivity six months postoperatively, which may be attributed to the natural decrease in dentin permeability observed following cavity preparation¹⁰.

Conclusion

The maintenance of pulp vitality remains at the core of deep caries management. By considering factors such as bacterial control, dentin thickness, and material selection, clinicians can optimize treatment approaches to preserve pulpal health and enhance the longevity of proximal restorations. Ultimately, a precise diagnosis, careful case selection, and adherence to evidence based protocols contribute to successful outcomes in the manage-

ment of deep proximal lesions.

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